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“A FLOWER, A BUTTERFLY, AND A STORM”

Past...

We were a caterpillar and a flower,
avoiding each other hour by hour;
I feared you came to steal my grace,
to take my fragrance, leave no trace.

Present...

Now you have become my butterfly,
lifting my petals when I dry;
you guard me from the harmful things,
even when it breaks your wings.

Future...

Our road ahead is not yet clear,
with storms and shadows drawing near;
if lightning strikes our fragile flower,
we kneel to God in that hard hour.

For love may bloom and love may bend,
but faith will guide us to the end.